

COMMUNICATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In today's process of globalization, interest and attention to learning foreign languages among peoples is increasing. It is known that when learning a language as a second language, it is necessary to acquire skills such as reading, listening, speaking and writing. This article talks about the importance and role of speaking competence in language learning. It also talks about how learning a second language can bring success to learners. Various methods for the development of speaking skills are highlighted. Experiments organized in order to determine the stages and levels of development of the speaking competence of language learners are highlighted. The analysis of some exercises used for the A1 and A2 stages of language teaching and the results expected from them are also shown.*

Keywords: *speaking skill, level, the stages of learning, intensive teaching, motivation, aspects of speech.*

Introduction: 21st century - at the same time as business is developing rapidly in the world, the need to work on the basis of agreements concluded in different languages in the process of international communication is increasing. In fact, this need is becoming the demand of the times. In order to make business activities more competitive in such companies and take a worthy place in the world markets, there is an increasing need for experts in the field who know several languages. Knowing the language will not only increase your position in the service (status), but also increase your income. Those living in the north-west of England who learned a language other than their mother tongue were paid more than £3,000 a year. According to the research of Philip Beresford, who published the list of the world's richest people in "Sunday List", knowing foreign languages brings an average of 145,000 pounds to Westerners in a year, etc. Companies dealing with foreign countries also pay extra for multilingual employees. Because such people can fill the cultural gaps between two countries, because they can easily understand their wishes and desires, work efficiency will increase and this will be useful for the company as well.[3.231-260]

Learning a new language opens the door to new opportunities. For example, in the process of learning a foreign language, you want to communicate with local people who speak that language, get to know them closely, and travel to that country. During the trip to this country, you can easily get to know the information you need without translators, have the opportunity to communicate with local residents, and improve your communication skills in the language you are learning. At the same time, the process of language learning can also develop foreign tourism.

Learning a language also helps to develop our mother tongue. Language learning is based on the grammar of the language being studied. In this process, language learners directly refer to the grammar of their native language and compare the grammar of their native language with the language they are learning: they compare and contrast. People think that they know the language well because they can communicate in their mother tongue without any difficulty. Because they rarely analyze the structure of their native language. Inadequate knowledge of the mother tongue is felt in the process of learning another language. Competences and skills acquired in the process of acquiring a second language make it easier to learn a third language by itself.

Learning a language will stimulate your interest in the culture of the speakers of that language. It is known that the process of language learning is closely related to culture. Nowadays, learning a language does not only mean mastering the language, but also preventing cultural or inter-ethnic conflicts that may occur due to ignorance of the culture, customs, lifestyle, history and origin of the nation that owns the language. It is also important to know the information that serves to obtain. This is an important tool of the language, while understanding the meaning of the word and being able to use it correctly, it expands our outlook, knowledge and increases our understanding of the world. English anthropologist E. B. Taylor gives the following opinion: "Culture is a complex globality." In order to gain deep knowledge of the language and acquire all abilities in language learning, a person should be aware of the art, culture, tradition, law, faith, history and other knowledge of the language owners. Because culture is the frame of mind of society. And language is a medium of culture. [3.38] Language learning is interesting and effective directly related to the culture and traditions of this nation. Attracts the learner's attention and increases his interest. Learning a language without culture is like cooking the national dish of that country without the aromatic spices of that country. Because not being aware of culture means not enjoying all the delights of this language. (If bread from Samarkand is baked elsewhere, it will not spoil for a few days. However, if it is baked in Samarkand itself, it will not spoil for a month. In the same way, uncivilized language will not remain in the memory for a long time.)

Learning a language - perfecting its linguistic aspect makes it easier to learn another language. Because the learner now knows how to learn a foreign language and that regular methods are effective for this process, the process of language learning becomes easier. In the process, it makes it easier for learners to learn about their similarities and differences by comparing languages. When the same language learning processes were observed by linguistic psychologists, it was found that the newly learned language occupies a large part of the memory in the human brain, and later, after the language is mastered, this information occupies a small amount of space. thinking, language control will not be necessary. The more perfectly learned languages are, the smaller their size in the brain will be, and they will remain firmly in the memory. [4.274]

Also, language learning develops the learner's ability to be creative. According to researchers, multilingual speakers are more creative than monolingual speakers. Learning a second language not only eliminates language barriers, but also encourages logical thinking and improves problem-solving skills. Language can increase creativity, if the learner cannot remember a word, he tries to find an alternative version of it, or encourages him to express it in several words, and learns to find several solutions to the same problem.

The process of language learning creates a sense of self-confidence in the learner. A learner can say "yes, I can" and that becomes his motto. The emergence of new skills, the ability to successfully speak the language you are learning also increases self-confidence. Language teaching methods also encourage the learner to think clearly. For example, the learner's self-confidence is important in the listening and speaking competencies of language learning. If the learner is not afraid of making mistakes in order to speak fluently in this language, he will be able to speak what he heard and know without the feelings of excitement and shyness, which will increase his confidence. can inspire the learner and can lead to the development of acquired experience and achievements in work. Because the basis of any success is hard work and self-confidence.

The main part: The process of globalization requires the development of all areas that act as its factors, along with the development of humanity. The main factor in the development of language is a person, and the means of communication is through speech (in both forms), which can be developed by humanity or, on the contrary, degraded. Since the life of the language is related to humanity, each person should not only learn it, enrich it, but also teach it and pass it on to the generations as a great legacy.

In recent years, realizing that not only learning the mother tongue, but also teaching it to representatives of other nationalities ensures the long-term survival of the language, finding new methods of teaching the language as a foreign language and putting it into practice a lot of work is being done on the application.

Initially, teaching a foreign language was considered to be the study of this language system, but in the following years, the purpose of teaching became the development of students' speech in a foreign language. It should be said that these goals in learning a foreign language are determined in an interdisciplinary relationship with mutual integrations in the sciences of linguistics and psychology, changes and social development of society, as well as the renewal of language teaching principles. Universalization, simplification of the taught language and the availability of easy and convenient methods of learning are important for the popularization of a foreign language. Today, there are many methods and methods of teaching a language as a second language or a foreign language. As part of our work, we would like to focus on the following methods:

Audiolingual method. The Russian linguist L. Sakayeva says that the evolution of the science of linguistics caused the emergence of this method[1]. This method includes the following factors:

- initially, to strengthen the oral speech skills of the foreign language learner;
- implementation of language teaching on the basis of various structures and speech patterns;
- using language-based exercises that require multiple repetitions of language material;
- teaching grammatical structure and vocabulary by comparing foreign language with mother tongue;
- pay great attention to pronunciation.

The main disadvantage of this method is that it contains a lot of mechanical exercises (exercises based on a certain pattern) and a lack of real speech development exercises. The founders of this method are Methodist scientists Ch. Friz and R. Ladolar. For example: Ch. Friz says: "The main content of the initial stage should be the study of structures"[2]. It is desirable that the formation of grammatical skills should be based on this. According to Ch. Frize and R. Lado, students should first remember the set of structures (sentences) used in oral speech.[6] Later, it is necessary to create new sentences on the basis of these structures, that is, skills and abilities must be formed. These are done through practical exercises.

Later, the audio-visual method began to take shape in the West. Its founders are Yugoslav Methodists P. Guberin and Frenchman Pierre Rivon, L. Hugueneim and others. This method is based on the development of the ability to quickly remember the language (language material) by hearing and seeing it. The main achievement of this method is that he learns the material of the language he is learning by connecting it to life situations. In fact, the basis of language learning is visual comprehension and listening comprehension. According to the authors, the method aims to

study topics that are common in everyday life (for example: home, household appliances, trade, etc.). Mastering the material is carried out mainly based on perception and through the extensive use of technical tools [2].

In connection with the issue of intensification of foreign language teaching, a number of works have been carried out in our country and abroad, and work in this field is being continued. They led to the emergence of new intensive methods.

One of the most important tasks is to create an atmosphere of speech communication in order to increase their activity in the lesson by using the internal capabilities of the learner's memory. The methods and various visual aids used by the teacher should be aimed at this goal. A psychological situation focused on speech communication is necessary to increase the activity of learners. E. I. Passov, one of the well-known Methodist scientists, said that the communicative approach currently used in foreign language teaching is an intensive form of teaching based on speech situations. [7]

It should be noted that audio-lingual and audiovisual methods cannot be used in intensive teaching practice. This is hindered by their principle side, that is, not relying on the native language of the language learner - not using it comparatively, learning, memorizing and creative exercises by imitating language imitation (language teaching and learning makes the process of mastering difficult). Hypnopedia, Relaxopedia - these methods give good results only in remembering language material, but cannot provide practical application in speech. That is why the famous scientist, prof. Gegechkori L.Sh. suggests to consider hypnopedia and relaxopedia as methods that can be used in teaching foreign languages.

In recent years, great attention has been paid to combining research in the fields of pedagogy, psychology, social psychology, and medicine in order to study the individual as an object and to determine all his creative possibilities. One of the important issues today is to direct students to new and creative thinking, to prepare them for life.

According to linguists and scientists L.Sh. Gegechkori and A.A. Leontev, Lozanov's methodology includes the above:

- 1) learning a large number of speech units;
- 2) to train students to use the language and vocabulary in the speech process, to use the learned speech unit in another situation;
- 3) Creating high motivation in learning;
- 4) Removing psychological barriers (shyness, fear, shyness) gives very good results.[8]

If a language teacher relies on Lozanov's methodology in each lesson, he will not only teach grammar structures and standardized speech units in the short term, but also requires a constant creative approach to eliminate shyness and self-doubt by motivating the learner. An experiment was conducted by the scientist at the Forestry Academy in Petrograd to teach students a foreign language based on an intensive method. The educational process was organized as follows:

1st semester - performing speech preparation exercises based on conscious learning of a foreign language;

2nd semester - development of dialogic speech based on the methodology of G. Lozanov;

Teaching the 3rd semester language material to a wide profile reading based on conscious learning;

4th semester - development of monologic speech based on the method of G. Lozanov;

5th semester - study of texts by specialization;[8]

This experiment was organized in order to determine the stages and levels of development of speech competence of language learners. In experimental organization, we consider a special approach to work with lexical units related to specialization appropriate. The ability of a language learner to speak in this language is an effective way to achieve a positive result in speech activity. In it, along with listening, oral communication is also carried out. The purpose of learning speech comes from the real needs and interests of students. Due to the fact that the goals and interests are different, it is necessary to pay attention to this in the development of communication opportunities through oral speech.

After completing the stages of speaking, the student can perform the following tasks:

- communicating in the context of direct communication, understanding and responding to the interlocutor's verbal statements (through verbal and non-verbal communication);
- to engage in dialogue on the areas, subjects and situations specified in the program for each stage;
- able to talk about surrounding things, environment, express personal opinion on any topic or give information.

The content of the speech is to express thoughts and convey information orally. Speaking as a type of speech activity is characterized by the following main parameters:

motive - desire or obligations;

goals and tasks - influencing the interlocutor, a way of self-expression;[7]

At the A1 stage of speaking competence, the following types of exercises are widely used to form and develop speaking skills:

1) a brief statement of the idea using small illustrations. For example:

- What do we see in the picture?
- What are they doing?
- What color are their clothes?

For example: Fill in the blanks with the appropriate words.

My name, hello, nice to meet you...

- Hello.
- Hello,
- What is your name?
- My name is Guli. How about yours?
- My name is Said.
- Nice to meet you
- Me too...

Such exercises help the language learner to verbally form ideas using ready-made templates for speaking. Listening exercises are also effective for forming and transitioning to the speaking stage. During the listening process, the language learner gets an idea of the tone and pronunciation of the language he is learning. That is why the role of the speaking stage is important in strengthening the acquired practical skills.

For example:

(An audio conversation on a certain topic will be read and broadcast)

I love ..., I hate

- Hello, Anwar!

- Hello, Lola!
- Anwar, what are the classes today?
- Today there are Uzbek language, history, mathematics lessons.
- I like math class because it is very interesting. Do you like this lesson too?
- no, I hate math. I like history class more.

The exercises given for the A2 level become more complicated compared to the A1 level of speaking competence, because the language learner can easily use adjectives and adverbs. The exercises used in the A1 stage can also be improved and used in the A2 stage. In addition, you can use a simplified version of the exercises with drawing graphics for the A2 level.

For example:

See the table. Describe Ali's class schedule.

Siz bunga qo'shilasizmi?

Conclusion: In conclusion, speaking competence is the main link of the language learning process. Competencies of reading, listening, and writing all serve to develop speaking skills. This is the main requirement for a student who teaches a certain language as a foreign language. It is necessary to start teaching the language learner through simple and acceptable methods and methods. For this, it is necessary to find convenient methods that facilitate learning and create new ones. Today, the Uzbek language, which is striving to be heard on the world stage, has such a huge task ahead of it.

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